

DIGITALIZATION OF NATURAL SCIENCE MUSEUM HOLDINGS: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS.

Sayidova Nilufar Bahodir kizi

Doctoral student (PhD) of the National

Institute of Fine Art and Design.

ORCID 0009-0006-6561-8647

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18927018>

Abstract. This article provides information on the issues of including museum collections and objects in the electronic catalog of the national museum fund, the advantages of digitization. In addition, several proposals are made on the problems and promising plans for digitizing funds.

Keywords. Museum fund, digitization, electronic catalog, SKM museum, KAMIC, natural science museums, exhibit, entomology.

Аннотация. В статье представлена информация о вопросах включения музейных коллекций и объектов в электронный каталог национального музейного фонда, преимуществах цифровизации. Кроме того, предложен ряд проблем и перспективных планов по цифровизации фондов.

Ключевые слова: музейный фонд, цифровизация, электронный каталог, музей СКМ, КАМИК, музей естественных наук, экспонаты, энтомология.

Аннотация. Ushbu maqolada muzey kolleksiyalari va ashyolarni milliy muzey fondining elektron katalogiga kiritish masalalari, raqamlashtirishning afzalliklari haqida ma’lumotlar berilgan. Bulardan tashqari fondlarni raqamlashtirishga oid muammo va istiqbolli rejalar haqida bir nechta takliflar kiritilgan.

Калит so`zlar. Muzey fondi, raqamlashtirish, electron katalog, SKM muzey, KAMIC, tabiiy-ilmiy muzeylar, eksponat, entomologiya.

Digitization of museum collections is the process of converting, systematizing and ensuring long-term storage of information about tangible and intangible heritage objects stored in museums using modern information technologies. As a result of the rapid development of digital technologies in the 21st century, the activities of museums include not only the storage and display of exhibits, but also their integration into the global information space. In this regard, the digitization of collections has become one of the priority areas of museology. Modern museum collections consist of various collections - historical artifacts, archaeological finds, natural specimens, works of art, documents and scientific materials, each of which has a special scientific, cultural and educational value. Along with the preservation and study of this rich heritage by traditional methods, the need to transfer them to a digital environment is associated with ensuring the safety of collections, effective use of information and increasing their accessibility to the general public. The digitization process includes:

- electronic registration of objects;
- creation of high-quality images;
- scientific description;
- formation of a metadata base;
- integration into information systems;

This process not only simplifies the management of museum collections, but also expands the possibilities for conducting scientific research, comparative analysis, and promoting cultural heritage on a large scale. For information, it can be said that the digitization process in museums in our country began in 2011. Initially, museum objects and collections began to be entered into the “SKM-MUZEY” electronic database. However, due to the shortcomings of this program (the search and editing system was faulty), the expected results were not achieved. Later, the “KAMIC” program was also developed. However, it also did not meet the requirements of specialists. Later, an electronic catalog of the National Museum Fund was created. Although not much time has passed since the creation of this program, it was widely promoted as more advanced and user-friendly than the previous “SKM” and “KAMIC” museum programs. Currently, all museums in our republic are working on the goskatalog.uz program. Objects are entered into this electronic database through the oksgoskatalog.uz website. The included items can be tracked and searched through the website goskatalog.uz. Museum items and museum collections in the fund's storage rooms are registered and stored on the basis of

“Ilmiy tadqiqotlarni amaliyotga joriy qilishning muammo va yechimlari” mavzusidagi onlayn xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallar to‘plami. NamDU - 2026-yil 20-21-fevral

relevant documents, but a separate instruction has not been developed for natural science museums. This is because most of the collections in museums of this specialization were collected through field expeditions. There is no special place allocated for their inclusion in a common electronic database. For example, the number of natural objects in the museums of our country is very large. If we take the example of the State Museum of Nature of Uzbekistan, which has the only natural science fund in Central Asia, the number of exhibits in the main fund of the museum is 363,059, and the number of exhibits in the scientific auxiliary fund is 1,265. If we refer to the numbers, 97 percent of the museum's collections are entomological collections. Unlike other collections, these collections are electronically digitized in groups (in the entomological collection box). This may cause a discrepancy in numbers. Zoological collections are listed as single specimens. Herbariums and carpological collections are listed by species and families. Currently, almost all exhibits are digitized, and it is even possible to take a virtual tour of the museum. The main goals of digitizing natural collections are:

Scientific goals:

- integration of collections into global scientific databases;
- simplification of taxonomic and geological research;
- protection of information about specimens from loss.

Management goals:

- strengthening control over funds;
- automation of inventory;
- reduction of the risk of loss and damage.

Cultural and educational goals:

- creation of virtual exhibitions;
- formation of a database open to the general public.

The most important advantages of digitizing museums include the following qualities:

Convenience. The ability to remotely observe museum collections from anywhere in the world without visiting them in person, as well as obtain additional information about the exhibition;

Safety. Protection of museum objects and collections from damage caused by natural and human factors;

Interactivity. The ability to interact with the viewer, the ability to attract them to the exhibition.

Popularity. Expanding the audience by placing museum collections on an online platform;

Communicative. The ability to connect with other industry platforms and widely promote museum collections through social media.

In conclusion, the digitization of museum collections is one of the important strategic directions of modern museology. It has ushered in a qualitatively new era in the preservation, management, and popularization of natural scientific heritage, in addition to cultural and scientific heritage. The process increases the efficiency of museum activities by ensuring the safety of the collection, improving its scientific description, and expanding the possibilities of using information. It also serves to integrate museum collections into the global scientific and cultural space, develop international cooperation, and ensure openness to the general public through the introduction of digital technologies. In the coming years, it is important to consistently continue the digitization processes of museum collections, introduce uniform standards, develop guidelines based on the specialization of each museum, train qualified personnel, and create expositions using modern technologies.

References

1. Гендина Н.И., Косолапова Е.В., Родионова Д.Д., Рябцева Л.Н. Цифровизация музеев и необходимость формирования информационной культуры музеологов. Вестник Томского государственного университета Культурология и искусствоведение. 2021. № 43.

2. Enrico Bertacchini and Federico Morando, The Future of Museums in the Digital Age: New Models of Access and Use of Digital Collections, International Journal of Arts Management · January 2011.

3. Фатхуллаев Р. Музей ишида замонавий ахборот технологияси // Мозийдан садо. – Тошкент, 2002. – № 2 (14). – Б. 8-11.

4. Tokyo National Art Museum Official Guide, 2021

5. Abdullaeva D. “Muzei faoliyatida zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining o‘rni.” O‘zbekiston Tarixi, 3(65), 2021y 112-117b

6. Ostonova, S. “O‘zbekiston muzeilarining raqamli transformatsiyasi: tajriba va natijalar.” Oliy Ta’lim, 7(2), 2022y 36-41b